

VIRTUAL REALITY AND AUGMENTED REALITY FOR IMMERSIVE LANGUAGE LEARNING

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***Abstract.** This article sheds light on the potential of virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) to create interactive and engaging language learning environments. It also gives general information about these technologies, their profound contribution to teaching and learning foreign languages and how to use them effectively in educational settings.*

***Keywords.** Languages, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, Technologies, Teaching, Education, Learning Environments*

Introduction. Nowadays virtual reality (VR) is one of the most powerful and invaluable tools in teaching and learning processes. VR is defined as a computer application that enables its users to experience immersive, three dimensional visual and audio simulations [1], as well as an active interaction in this new learning atmosphere. VR gives a great opportunity for both teachers and students as multiple senses (touch, sense of the heat, smell) can participate in the use of it. AR is used to describe a set of technological elements that permit the user to have a clear image of the real world while using a device that generates extra graphic information. This means that the real physical world is mixed with other virtual elements [2], making students enjoy the learning process. AR requires no special equipment, as most of students own a smartphone with camera, they are able to use it anywhere.

Main part. One of the important features of VR is immersion, which enhances the situated experience of user. This aspect allows second language (L2) and foreign language (FL) learners to combine learning an additional language with an intercultural experience beyond geographical limitations with no need to step out of the classroom or leave their home countries [3]. Another

important feature supported by VR applications is interaction, which provides users with a special channel of interpersonal communication. One of the most significant developments in education today is learning by doing, experiencing, or creating. Based on distinct pedagogical goals, the numerous VR applications for language learning can be loosely divided into five categories: entertainment, social networking, visual experiences, operation, and creation [4]. In a VR-integrated classroom, students can engage in activities that extend beyond print-based reading and writing and support the development of language skills, including communication, writing, and reading, through the use of technology. There are also many benefits using Augmented reality (AR) in language learning and teaching. The first advantage of using AR in education, and language instruction in particular, is that it may make it easier for students to comprehend concepts that are thought of as abstract. AR offers accessible learning materials anywhere and anytime. Instead of using paper-based textbooks, models, posters, or printed manual, it offers portable and less expensive learning materials [2]. It offers contextual, authentic, and situational learning environments. For instance, Chen (2020) conducted an experimental study with 97 sixth graders in Taiwan to examine the impact of AR movies on language learners' motivation, achievement, and satisfaction from the standpoint of scaffolding. The application and methodology used in this study was AR video-enhanced learning (ARVEL), which means that students learned insect-related vocabulary by using AR video-enhanced materials. According to the findings, the ARVEL technique was effective in raising student happiness, intrinsic motivation, and achievement. The significance of combining AR technology with additional multimedia components, such films and instant prompts, was demonstrated by this study [5].

Conclusion. There are so many advantages of using AR and VR during learning and teaching languages as it helps not only to improve basic skills in language proficiency like reading, writing, speaking and vocabulary but also it enhances critical and creative thinking of students by providing them with the

imagination of abstract things, additionally building strong relationships with people through their feature of interaction.

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